

Number of close friends and attitude towards drugs and alcohol in Youths of Ahmedabad

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Abstract—Background: Enough importance has never been given to friends as stress busters where one can share different things and try to solve the matters according to their suggestions of with their help. The study was to assess the role the close friends play in preventing or promoting the attitude towards drugs and alcohol

Objectives: To assess the effect that close friends have on the attitude towards drugs and alcohol in youths of Ahmedabad

Method: A sample size of 180 youths was used which consisted of 80 males and 80 females was collected from various collages of Ahmedabad irrespective of their stream and year of study was collected then their t-value was found out to check the degree of relation between their number of close friends and their attitude towards drugs and alcohol.

Result: the analysis shows that the ‘t’ value is not significant so it proves that more the number of close friends the less is the chance of positive attitude towards drugs and alcohol

Conclusion: Youths should have more close friends so that they stay away from drugs and alcohol

Keywords: near friends, attitude towards drugs and alcohol, youths of Ahmedabad

I. INTRODUCTION

The question which arose for research was “Does number of close friends of an individual affect their attitude towards drugs and alcohol?” The study was supposed to answer the questions like Does more close friends create the need for substance abuse? Or Does more close friends stop a person from abusing substance? This being raised the target people were decided to be the youths as this is considered the period of volatility among all periods. This period is also the period of some decisions which affect for the life time and can make or break any person and his/her future. The next choice of the city was Ahmedabad as all the things are considered to be available in this city of Gujarat.

Subjects were chosen randomly from the collages without considering their stream of study and also without considering their year of collage also the collages were also picked randomly so as to ensure that the decision is not biased. It was a pen and paper based survey where a scale was

More close friends also mean that the person is extrovert and less number of close friends can mean that the person is introvert and may not like to share things with friends. Sharing is an important part of the human nature and healthy sharing of personal things release the tension and it’s an important aspect of man as a social animal. With all these things in mind the study was considered as necessary.

For these study 80 male students and 80 female students data was collected from them by asking them to fill the questionnaire

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dwivedi and Dwivedi (2024). A study on attitude towards alcohol and drug among high secondary Hindi and English medium students. The study revealed that there was good difference in the attitude towards alcohol and drugs and in the high secondary Hindi and English medium students

Zahin, Roy, Sinha, Maheshwari, Sethi and Patel (2023). Epidemiological correlates of substance abuse among in-facility clients of de-addiction and rehabilitation centers of district Dehradun: A cross-sectional study. Both ‘peer pressure’ and ‘curiosity’ play a major role in substance use. It was found that age and level of education were important factors for substance

abuse. Sensitivity and capacity building of both providers and the community is for the prevention and control of substance abuse the establishment of de-addiction and rehabilitation centers at the district level should be given priority.

Thangavel V (2023) Research on alcohol consumption and physical illness in India: Government's responsibility to stop alcohol from reaching students in high school and college. It is critical to understand the prevalence and costs of alcohol consumption in different States because alcohol consumption policies and laws are different across different States within nation. This community-based cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out in various states across the country. People who consume alcohol are more likely to experience health issues like hypertension, gastrointestinal issues, and mental problems. There are many issues related to human family welfare, organ functioning problems and different illness.

Thakkar and Deb (2022). The influence of peer pressure on drinking in Indian youth: A mixed-methods study. Youth is a period when one is more likely to engage in things that have a lasting and negative impact on their health regarding youth-alcohol-related behaviors. The emphasis is on the role of peer pressure and self-control as well as the function of their self-restraint to resist peer pressure when it comes to drinking.

Shah, Dar, Kumari P, Shiekh, Mushtaq and Tallie (2022). Socio-demographic and clinical profile of treatment-seeking drug abusers attending a hospital in South Kashmir: A cross-sectional hospital-based study. Young adults were found to be using mainly opioids even though poly-substance formed the majority. More than sixty percent of patients used intravenous drugs and therefore the infections rate was very high. Peer pressure and curiosity were the most stated reasons for starting of substance. More than half of cases had past history of failed attempts at abstinence.

Narasimha, Arvind, Holla, Tadeballi, Kandasamy, and Murthy (2022). Practice and attitude of doctors towards patients with substance use: A study from south India. Positive efforts must be under-taken to train the doctors in the effective management substance related disorders. Attitudes of the doctors influence brief interventions. Programs aimed towards changing the attitudes of doctors can bring meaningful changes in their practices.

Nadkarni, Tu, Garg, Gupta, Bhatia, Tiwari, Heath, Wen, Fernandes and Velleman (2022). Alcohol use among adolescents in India: a systematic review. Some of the important correlates associated with alcohol consumption are being male, higher age, study related difficulties, parental use of alcohol or tobacco, non-contact sexual abuse and continuation of violence.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

This study is to assess the quality of the friendship and also the number of close friends and its effect on the attitude towards drugs and alcohol in youths. Knowing this attributes may ease the concern of the parents and well-wishers about the friends of the youths.

IV. OBJECTIVES

To study the relation between the number of close friends and attitude towards drugs and alcohol in youths of Ahmedabad

Hypothesis

H0 There is no significant relation between the number of close friends and attitude towards drugs and alcohol in youths of Ahmedabad

H1 There is no significant relation between the number of close friends and attitude towards drugs and alcohol in male youths of Ahmedabad

H2 There is no significant relation between the number of close friends and attitude towards drugs and alcohol in female youths of Ahmedabad

V. METHODOLOGY

Sample and source of sample

Students of various collages of Ahmedabad

Sample Size

Sample size is 160

That is 80 male students and 80 Female students of various streams irrespective of their year of collage

Variables

Independent variable

No of friends

Dependent variable

Attitude towards drugs and alcohol;

Scale used

Attitude towards drug and alcohol” by Dr. Poorva Jain and Dr. Amit Deolia

VI. STATICAL ANALYSIS

Mean, standard deviation, standard error mean, difference, t-value and level of significance are used as stastical techniques.

Table 1

Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	't' value	Level of Significance
No.of friends	160	14	10.16	103	-31.48	Not Significant
Attitude towards drug and alcohol	160	54	12.45	155		

In the “t” distribution table at df =100 the “t” value at.01 level is 2.62. The obtained “t” value (-31.48) is much less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 2

Female Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	't' value	Level of Significance
No.of friends	80	11	8.93	79.73	-24.97	Not Significant
Attitude towards drug and alcohol	80	53	12.11	147		

In the “t” distribution table at df =80 the “t” value at.01 level is 2.639. The obtained “t” value(-24.97) is less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3

Male Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	't' value	Level of Significance
No.of friends	80	18	10.1	101.92	-20.38	Not Significant
Attitude towards drug and alcohol	80	55	12.71	162		

In the “t” distribution table at df =80 the “t” value at.01 level is 2.639. The obtained “t” value(-20.38) is less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

Chart for Female

Chart for Males

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As the analysis shows that the 't' value is not significant so it proves that more the number of close friends the less is the chance of positive attitude towards drugs and alcohol

VIII. CONCLUSION

Youths should have more close friends so that they stay away from drugs and alcohol

Limitations and suggestions: In this study a small sample size was used so the results may vary when taking large sample size. The demography change also can affect the results. The study was not aimed at any particular stream or the year of study so if these factors are considered then also the result may vary.

Youths are advised to have more close friends and share things with them and also the parents should first check the quality of the group of youths and then allow them to mingle and perform their activities.

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